

Optimizing Academic Pathways: A Cutting-Edge LSTM Approach to Engineering Course Recommendations for Career Growth¹

Ashalakshmi R

Department of Computer Science, Karpagam Academy of Higher Education,
Eachanari, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India

S Hemalatha

Department of Computer Science, Karpagam Academy of Higher Education,
Eachanari, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract

The engineering field provides numerous courses, posing a challenge for students to navigate and select the most suitable one aligned with their interests, academic goals, and career ambitions. In order to solve this problem, engineering course recommendation systems (CRS) have evolved as useful tools which use data analysis, artificial intelligence, and personalized algorithms to offer students individualized course recommendations. The CRS is very important for students because it gives individualized assistance, save time and effort, encourages exploration, improves academic performance and development, fit with professional goals, enables flexibility and adaptation, and facilitates decision-making. Career counseling services play a crucial role in a student's academic performance and had great impact on their future professional achievements. The CRS should be adaptable enough to consider changes in the student's situation and the course structure. This paper proposed an effective engineering CRS based on LSTM. The proposed model is evaluated on student dataset with 10 features. The experiment's findings shows that the proposed engineering CRS performed better than conventional recommendation systems, with an accuracy of 99.76%. The suggested model accurately predicts the appropriate course after examining the student's personality and performance.

Keywords

Career Selection, Recommendation System, Artificial Intelligence, Recurrent Neural Network, MBTI.

¹Address Author Correspondence to Ashalakshmi R at ash.lekshmi@gmail.com

Accepted: 12 June 2024 / Published online: 25 June 2024

© The Author(s), 2024. Paper ID, 100350.

1. Introduction

The advancement of information technology, the emergence of various career development theories, and the increasing competitiveness in the job market have transformed the career choices into a complex and systematic process [1]. A person's entire future is impacted by the immensely significant decision of choosing a career path. According to the research, investigating possible careers before settling on one, improves future career performance and satisfaction [2]. Therefore, it is important to recognize and identify the factors influencing adolescent career exploration. In the modern day, selecting a career route leaves many students perplexed. This could be as a result of the diversity of human skills. Students were influenced by a number of variables while deciding on a career route, including their environment, educational achievements and personal abilities. Furthermore, a significant number of students are inclined towards pursuing career that align with their parents' preferences and interests. Some students choose their career based on great financial potential, while others pursue their passions regardless of their level of success [3]. The study delves into the factors that shaping career decisions among STEM students in a South African university, by highlighting the significance of understanding, the students' perspectives for tailored support. Through qualitative analysis of 203 responses, themes emerged, revealing the impact of familial influence, personal traits, and anticipated outcomes on career choices. This discussion sheds light on the nuanced interplay between interpersonal, intrapersonal and outcome expectations in the career decision-making process among STEM students, which offers insight for educators and policymakers to give better guidance to the students towards fulfilling career paths [4]. Depending on the circumstances, several issues with course selection may arise. For example, there are many different courses offered in a university context, and issues occur if students are unfamiliar with the options. Similar to this, choosing courses should consider a student's aptitude and professional interests. The system should also be able to handle convenience to student's conditions and modify the course structures.

In the contemporary educational environment, students have a wide range of options when it comes to select their courses that match their interests, skills, and professional goals. Especially in light of the numerous course options, making informed judgements might be difficult. In order to overcome this difficulty, CRS that consider elements like personality traits and academic performance have become important tools for guiding students in their course selecting process. These recommendation systems can offer personalized recommendations that are catered to certain students by utilizing the power of artificial intelligence. This customized method considers not only the student's academic performance and background, but also their own personality qualities, which can have a big impact on their preferences and learning preferences.

The academic and professional preferences of the students are significantly influenced by their personality features. For example, an extroverted student might do well in groups, but an introverted student would prefer working alone. A student's unique tastes and learning style can be considered by CRS and it recommends courses by recording and analyzing personality features. Additionally, a student's academic achievement, as indicated by their grades or marks, offers insightful information about their strengths and limitations. The recommendation system will be able to provide a more

thorough knowledge of the student's abilities and areas of interest with the inclusion of this data. The block diagram in Figure 1 provides a general representation of a CRS.

Figure 1: General Block Diagram of Course Recommendation System

Students can gain various advantages by using a CRS that takes into account of both academic success and personality qualities. Firstly, they may avoid wasting time and effort on course research and evaluation. Instead, individuals are given recommendations that are tailored to their needs and compatible with their skills. Second, these platforms might extend their perspectives and open their eyes to new educational prospects by introducing students to the courses they might not have otherwise found. As students are more likely to engage in classes that connect with their particular qualities, the personalized recommendations can also help to make learning more enjoyable and engaging. However, it's crucial to remember that while CRS provide insightful guidance, they should be viewed as helpful tools rather than final decision-makers. Students should also take into account of their own passions, long-term goals, and advisers or mentors in order to make sure that the chosen courses are in sync with their overall educational and career aims.

One of the most crucial elements in a nation's development is educational system, which serves as the foundation for an individual's output, growth, and labour in the field of development. Therefore, it is crucial to educate people to encourage critical thinking, understanding, research, and problem-solving [5]. The administration and direction of the economic and social spheres greatly depend on the crucial contributions of individual's education. The lives of people can be affected by new ideas that engineers, business, and technology can produce and there by the economic condition of the nation [6]. The correct engineering courses should be chosen because they have a direct impact on students' academic success, employment opportunities, and personal development. Due to the wide array of engineering courses available, students may face challenges in selecting courses that align with their interests, objectives, and academic capabilities. Engineering course selection systems that incorporate academic performance and personality attributes have become useful tools to help students in solving their difficulty by assisting them in making informed and individualized decisions. The preferences, interests in learning, and career inclinations of a person are significantly influenced by their personality features. These systems are able to learn more about a student's innate proclivities, social orientation, and

preferred work situations by combining personality assessments like the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) [7] or the Big Five personality traits [8,24,25]. With the help of this data, the system may suggest engineering courses that connect with the student's personality traits and interests, resulting in a greater match between the course material and their unique tastes. Additionally, considering a student's academic achievement during their higher academics offers significant insights into their strengths, limitations, and subject-specific aptitudes. These systems can determine a student's academic ability and areas of interest by examining their marks or grades in pertinent disciplines. In order to maximize the use of the student's current knowledge and skills, this information suggests engineering courses that correspond with their academic accomplishments and areas of expertise. Systems for choosing engineering courses based on personality and higher studies have a number of benefits for students. They help students in two ways, Firstly, they give them personalized recommendations that fit with their unique interests and academic strengths, which helps them make better-informed selections. This can spare students from having to manually study and evaluate a variety of courses, which may take a lot of time and become very difficult. Secondly, these systems can assist students in exploring engineering specializations that they may not have previously thought about, expanding their horizons and introducing them to fresh fields of study and career options. The personalized recommendations contribute to enhancing the enjoyment and fulfilment of learning by ensuring that the students are matched with classes that align with their personalities and academic strengths, ultimately increasing their motivation and performance. Engineering course selection tools do provide useful information, but it is important to remember that they should not take the place of human direction, introspection, or academic adviser interaction. These technologies act as supplementary tools, enhancing students' ability to make decisions by offering data-driven insights. When deciding on their final engineering course choices, students should also take their long-term objectives, personal hobbies, and other pertinent considerations into account. These systems enable students to select courses that match their interests, aptitudes, and future career aspirations, and it fosters a more successful and fulfilling educational experience. They accomplish this by considering the interaction between a student's personality traits, academic performance, and engineering course offerings. This paper presents an engineering CRS based on an LSTM model.

2. Literature Review

A number of techniques that can be utilized to construct the CRS which is proposed by Huynh-Ly Thanh-Nhan *et al.* [9]. Students can use CRS to predict their learning outcomes in advance and to choose the right courses so that they can create better study schedules. These strategies are evaluated and examined using a real data set. After deciding on an appropriate method, the CRS construction framework is presented. The testing results indicated that the suggested recommendation system had a higher level of prediction accuracy, but it still needs to be improved. In a MOOC setting, Hao Zhang *et al.* [10] demonstrated a customized recommendation system based on DBN. The utilization of DBN (Deep Belief Network) in this system was advantageous due to its exceptional capabilities in function approximation, feature extraction, prediction classification, and various other domains. The user's course interests were determined by combining the feature vector of the MOOC platform with the user's

preferences. Meanwhile, DBN supervised learning used the course grade as the class label. The experiment was run on a real MOOC platform and contrasted with a number of conventional recommendation techniques. This work combines the RMSE instances for Content-Based, KNN, SVD, and RBM on the data set to demonstrate the classification and prediction capabilities of DBNCF. The suggested success percentage is 77.42%. The main drawback of the suggested method is that it cannot process high dimension sparse matrices using the SVD method. Although the model convergence rate is not optimistic, the RBM-based suggestion has a decent predictive recommendation ability. CourseQ, developed by Boxuan Ma *et al.* [11], is a Course Recommendation System (CRS) that integrates interactive visualization and recommendation techniques, aiming to enhance the examination and comprehension of recommendation processes through an interactive interface. The primary goal of this work has been to satisfy the various demands of various students and enable them to investigate material in a variety of ways depending on the circumstances. Although the CourseQ received positive feedback for its usability and the quality of its recommendations, there were some users who desired an even simpler interaction experience. The main drawback is that additional quantitative objective metrics might have been added to the qualitative evaluation, which primarily focused on the user's opinion of the interaction idea and the quality of the outcomes. An innovative deep learning-based course recommender system (DECOR) was put forth by Qinglong Li and Jaekyeong Kim [12], which meticulously records high-level user behaviors and course attribute information. The DECOR model shows promise in alleviating the problem of information overload, tackling the challenges posed by sparsity in high-dimensional data, and achieving remarkable performance in extracting valuable feature information. The effectiveness of the suggested model was assessed using the real-world dataset, and its performance was contrasted with that of the conventional recommendation systems. The results of the experiment demonstrated that the DECOR model outperforms traditional methods and provides more dependable recommendations. The suggested method has various drawbacks that must be considered. Designing recommendation algorithms based on deep learning is a challenging and intricate task that requires expertise in knowledge engineering. Second, many researchers have faced significant difficulties while attempting to study course recommender systems in online education contexts. The absence of openly available standardized datasets for evaluating recommender systems is the underlying cause for this issue. Third, the outcomes of this study focused mostly on technical elements of algorithms for recommending courses. It is not capable of behavioral research. A course recommender system for the e-learning platform was created by Karim Dahdouh *et al.* [13]. With the use of the association rules mining technique, it seeks to identify connections between the activities of the student's courses in order to assist the student in selecting more pertinent learning resources. The FP-growth algorithm was used to put the CRS into practice. The provided recommendation engine is adaptable and simple to integrate into various learning environments, like MOOCs. The experiment's findings showed that the suggested approach effectively improved the calibre of students' decisions, guided them through the learning process, and offered customized online learning programmes to match the demands of the students.

T B Lalitha and P S Sreeja [14] presented the SDL approach as a solution to the problem of e-learning recommendation, utilizing recommendation system called PSDLR to accomplish the goals. The e-learning materials are initially analyzed and classified using collaborative and content-based filtering techniques built over a qualitative and quantitative content check. Then the materials are divided into learning materials for beginners, intermediate learners, and advanced learners. Individual requirements and demands are then gathered. Finally, the two modules worked together to create the recommendation system. The findings showed that the suggested recommendation system effectively encourages towards correct guidance on personalized elearning recommendations to the self-directed learners in accordance with their specific needs. Sequence-based methods for CRS were proposed by Ren Wang and Osmar R. Zaiane [15]. Three distinct sequence-related strategies are put into practice. The strategies are finally merged into a comprehensive method and ranking methods are suggested to favor shortening the programme. The experiment's findings showed that all three methods can improve students' performance on various scales. The dependency graph serves as the foundation for the most effective recommendation approach, and acceptance rates for recommended courses are positively correlated with performance. Manar Qamhieh *et al.* [16] developed a personalized career-path recommender system (PCRS) that aids aspiring engineering students in choosing their academic specialization by considering various factors such as academic achievements, personality traits, and involvement in extracurricular activities. The primary objective of PCRS is to act as knowledgeable mentors who assist students in making challenging decisions by analyzing their academic and personal backgrounds. The fuzzy-logic intelligence used in the PCRS design has two key input parameters. The outcomes of the trial demonstrated that the suggested recommendation method can help high school students who want to pursue engineering degrees. A classification method was developed for a career recommendation system by Robert Masika *et al.* [17]. A student's acceptable career was predicted using a variety of classification techniques. The study found that job suitability predictions for students can be made using classification algorithms. All of the utilized classifiers provided a prediction accuracy of more than 88%. The results of the experiment showed that classification models made up of several classifiers might be used to forecast suitable careers for secondary students.

Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, there's a surging demand for online education platforms, yet selecting suitable course content remains challenging due to varying user knowledge structures. Consequently, course recommender systems play a crucial role in enhancing learning efficiency. While Collaborative Filtering (CF) has been widely utilized in existing systems, the emergence of deep learning models addresses issues like data sparsity and scalability. Li Q and Kim J [18] introduces DECOR, a novel deep learning-based course recommender system designed to capture nuanced user behaviors and course attributes, mitigating information overload and achieving superior recommendation performance. Through empirical evaluations with real-world datasets, DECOR demonstrates improved recommendation accuracy and robustness compared to traditional methods.

A recommendation system for online learners was put forth by Jianwen Feng and Xuan Lin [19] and is based on a knowledge map with several functional modules that are constructed. The loss function is utilized to optimize the recommendation model. Furthermore, a recommendation algorithm is developed

to select the dataset, to evaluate the system using a knowledge map, and primarily gauge its performance. It also makes it possible for the knowledge map and recommendation module to collaboratively study each other's implicit properties in order to produce recommendations for online learners. The overall performance is excellent due to the design and experimentation of the knowledge map-based algorithm used for online learners' courses, which can enhance the implementation of the recommendation function. A multi-agent and content-based CRS for an academic e-learning platform was proposed by Meryem Amane *et al.* [20]. The disadvantage of a suggestion mechanism employing collaborative filtering is successfully addressed by the suggested strategy. The findings of the trial indicated that the recommended courses closely match the user preferences. An ontology-based tool for personalized course recommendations was created by Mohammed Essmat Ibrahim *et al.* [21]. The objective is to increase the effectiveness and efficiency to direct the students towards right path. The recommendation system considers various factors such as user information, course material, and knowledge about the learning domain in order to provide relevant suggestions. This approach facilitates the easy sharing and utilization of learning components among different e-learning systems. It makes use of certain ontology to automatically determine what courses a system should search for and what courses a student should take. A CRS was created by Ammar A. Neamah and Amer S. El-Ameer [22] using KNN and a Naive Bayes classifier. The accuracy of recommendations can be improved and several issues with conventional recommender systems can be solved by using multiple classifiers in a recommender system. A content-based recommender system can be created using KNN and Naive Bayes classifiers. As a result of their easy procedures, they can produce good accuracy and performance results. Jindan Tan *et al.* [23] proposed an innovative approach called the Attentional Manhattan Siamese Long Short-Term Memory (AMSLSTM) network along with an autoencoder that utilizes course descriptions to generate course relevance. Additionally, the model incorporates self-attention to effectively discern the student's preference level across different subject areas.

CRS have grown in favor in educational settings to help students make wise selections about their academic pursuits. These systems provide helpful guidance, but there are some limitations that must be recognized. The main limitations of conventional CRS are listed below. The majority of CRS base their suggestions on user information including past course history, grades, and preferences. However, they frequently struggle to make suggestions that are highly personalized because of a lack of knowledge or their inability to fully understand the subtleties of different learning styles and interests. This may lead to general recommendations that don't necessarily fit each student's particular requirements. CRS heavily relies on the database or course catalogue that is readily accessible. Recommendations may be wrong or incomplete if the catalogue is outdated or incomplete. Additionally, these algorithms could be unable to recommend courses from external websites or organizations, which would restrict the range of choices open to students. The hobbies and professional aspirations of students can change throughout time. However, because they frequently rely on past data, CRS frequently has trouble adapting to these changes. As a result, the recommendations could not adequately represent students' changing goals and interests. It's possible that CRS does not have access to current information about things like course availability, scheduling problems, or changes to course curricula. This limitation may lead to recommendations that do not consider real-world

restrictions, which may lead to students being advised to enroll in courses that may not suit their academic goals. Some recommendation systems generate recommendations largely based on popularity data, such as enrollment rates or average ratings. While these indicators can give a broad sense of the caliber of a course, they might not always represent each student's unique needs, preferences, or learning preferences. Students can thereby miss out on less well-liked but better-suited courses for their particular interests. CRS frequently emphasize academic variables like prerequisites, major requirements, and credit hours but may neglect other crucial factors like extracurricular interests, skill development, or transdisciplinary chances. Students may be prevented from exploring a variety of academic opportunities or seeking interdisciplinary learning because of this restrictive emphasis.

3. Materials and Methods

In this paper, a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based engineering CRS was developed using student personality and academic performance. It all started with gathering the appropriate dataset. Data preprocessing and exploratory data analysis were performed after the datasets were collected. The LSTM based CRS received the pre-processed data. Finally, the performance of CRS was assessed. Figure 2 depicts the schematic diagram of the proposed CRS.

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of the Proposed Engineering Course Recommendation System

3.1. Dataset Description

The dataset was obtained from Kaggle. The dataset has 11 Columns and 2560 Rows. The dataset includes ten features that are related to both academic achievement and personality. 16 different engineering courses are provided as the ground truth data. The sample data is shown in figure 3.

	MBTI Score	Extroverts	Senses	Thinkers	Perceivers	Physics	Chemistry	Maths	10th %	Plus 2%	Class Label
0	1	0	0	0	0	61	71	81	91	81	Chemical Engineering
1	2	0	0	0	1	62	72	82	92	82	Civil Engineering
2	3	0	0	1	0	63	73	83	93	83	Electrical Engineering
3	4	0	0	1	1	64	74	84	94	84	Mechanical Engineering
4	5	0	1	0	0	65	75	85	91	85	Aerospace Engineering

Figure 3: Sample Data for Dataset

The MBTI assessment is a well-known psychological tool used to categorize individuals into different personality types, and the outcomes are commonly known as MBTI scores. The MBTI test utilizes a set of questions to assess individuals' preferential comparisons across four pairs of opposing factors.

- **Extraversion (E) vs. Introversion (I):** These factors examine whether people direct their energy towards the external world (extraversion) or inwardly towards themselves (introversion).
- **Sensing (S) vs. Intuition (N):** It delves into the manner in which individuals gather and understand information, either by concentrating on precise particulars and empirical data (sensing) or by discerning patterns, potential consequences, and underlying meanings (intuition).
- **Thinking (T) vs. Feeling (F):** This contrast investigates how individuals make decisions, either through rational analysis (thinking) or by drawing upon their emotions and personal values (feeling).
- **Judging (J) vs. Perceiving (P):** It illustrates how individuals interact with the external environment, either through deliberate and structured behaviours (judging) or through spontaneous and flexible investigation (perceiving).

Individuals receive a four-letter personality type code expressing their preferences in each dichotomy after responding to the evaluation questions. These four-letter codes, which stand for the MBTI scores, offer information about a person's personality traits and behavioural inclinations. Each personality type is linked to particular traits, aptitudes, and areas of improvement. The results enable people to comprehend their innate tendencies, communication preferences, methods of decision-making, and ideal working surroundings. Figure 4 illustrates the 16 MBTI personality types. The four dichotomy has values of 0 and 1. Table 1 contains descriptions of the four dichotomy values found in the dataset.

Table 1: Representation of MBTI personality types in the dataset

Column	Value	Indication
Extroverts	0	Introvert
	1	Extrovert
Senses	0	Intuitive
	1	Senses
Thinkers	0	Feeler
	1	Thinker
Perceivers	0	Judger
	1	Perceiver

ISTJ Practical, reserved, insensitive and judgmental	ISTP Independent, confident, insensitive and gets bored easily	ISFJ Sensitive, practical, neglects their own needs and dislikes change	ISFP Peaceful, quiet, reserved and dislikes conflicts
INFJ Compassionate, creative, overly sensitive and holds high expectations from others	INFP Loyal, devoted, idealistic and tends to take things personally	INTJ Hardworking, self-confident, judgmental and overly analytical	INTP Logical, objective, insensitive and have problems following rules
ESTP Resourceful, observant, impulsive and dramatic	ESTJ Practical, realistic, insensitive and argumentative	ESFP Resourceful, practical, impulsive and gets bored easily	ESFJ Organized, loyal, needy and controlling
ENFP Enthusiastic, creative, gets stressed easily and struggles to follow rules	ENFJ Empathetic, affectionate, indecisive and manipulative	ENTP Innovative, creative, insensitive and unfocused	ENTJ Organized, confident, impatient and stubborn

Figure 4: 16 Personality Types of MBTI

Based on different combinations of the choices, there are a total of 16 possible varieties. A type is denoted by four letters, for example, an ESTJ stands for extraverted, sensing, thinking, and judging. Each form has advantages and disadvantages, and there is no superior type. This evaluation test can help people comprehend the sixteen various personality types that emerge from the interplay between their preferences and validate their preferences on each of the four dichotomies. The dataset's 16 class labels represent the various engineering courses. The dataset also includes information on the student's academic performance, such as grades from the 10th and 12th grades and grades for different subjects (Physics, Chemistry, and Math).

3.2. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is essential for assuring data quality, optimizing model performance, managing various data kinds, minimizing overfitting, enabling swift calculations, and improving the readability of analysis results. This step is vital in the data analysis process as it enhances the reliability and relevance of the insights derived from the data. The process of data preprocessing entails converting raw data into a compatible format which is suitable for analysis and modeling objectives. Data preprocessing involves data cleaning, handling missing values and data normalization.

Data cleaning encompasses the detection and correction of errors, discrepancies, and inaccuracies within a dataset, with the goal of improving its overall quality and reliability. The process of cleaning a.csv file normally entails numerous phases, such as entering the data into Microsoft Excel, finding inaccurate numbers, and dealing with duplicates. The treatment of duplicates is a crucial step since they might bias the study and produce false results. Inconsistent data types, outliers, and formatting errors are a few other problems that may need to be dealt with during data cleaning. It is also crucial to standardize the data to ensure accuracy and consistency across the entire dataset. Depending on the amount and complexity of the dataset, data cleansing can be a difficult and time-consuming procedure.

In data analysis, it is a critical phase that can assist avoid mistakes and ensure accurate and trustworthy results. In order to maintain accuracy and dependability over time, data cleansing is an ongoing activity that necessitates frequent monitoring and updating.

Data preprocessing involves handling missing values because they can provide skewed or incorrect analysis results. The type of the data, the degree of missingness, the goals of the analysis, and the presumptions made about the mechanism for managing missing data all influence the choice of missing value handling technique. The gathered dataset does not contain any missing values, as can be shown after null value verification.

The method of scaling one or more parameters to be between 0 and 1, where the highest value of each attribute is 1 and the minimum is 0, is known as data normalization. When the data distribution is unknown, this strategy is beneficial. The complete dataset is converted into a numerical dataset after using the Label Encoder approach. All datasets with text labels can be converted into numerical datasets using Label Encoder.

3.3. Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) is an essential stage in comprehending and highlighting the key traits, trends, and connections found in a dataset. Before using more sophisticated analysis tools, it aids in the identification of key traits, the detection of outliers, and the generation of early insights. The two most common EDA techniques are data visualization and summary statistics. Basic summary statistics for numerical variables are calculated with the help of summary statistics, encompassing measures such as average, middle value, most frequently occurring value, variability, and division into four equal parts. These statistics offer preliminary understanding of the data and aid in the identification of central patterns, variability, and distributions. Figure 5 shows the statistical analysis of the dataset. Table 2 has a count for each class labels.

	MBTI Score	Extroverts	Senses	Thinkers	Perceivers	Physics	Chemistry	Maths	10th %	Plus 2%
count	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000	2560.000000
mean	8.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	65.541016	78.191797	82.801953	82.168359	81.654297
std	4.610673	0.500098	0.500098	0.500098	0.500098	2.868465	9.273425	10.330237	10.202760	10.157976
min	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	61.000000	61.000000	61.000000	61.000000	61.000000
25%	4.750000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	63.000000	71.000000	74.750000	74.000000	73.000000
50%	8.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	0.500000	66.000000	78.000000	86.000000	85.000000	84.000000
75%	12.250000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	68.000000	86.000000	92.000000	91.000000	91.000000
max	16.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	70.000000	94.000000	94.000000	94.000000	94.000000

Figure 5: Statistical Analysis of Data

Table 2: Count of Class labels

Class Label	Count
Chemical Engineering	160
Civil Engineering	160
Electrical Engineering	160
Mechanical Engineering	160
Aerospace Engineering	160
Agricultural Engineering	160
Biomedical Engineering	160
Computer Hardware Engineering	160
Environmental Engineering	160
Industrial Engineering	160
Marine Engineering	160
Materials Engineering	160
Mining and Geological Engineering	160
Nuclear Engineering	160
Petroleum Engineering	160
Health and Safety Engineering	160

EDA relies heavily on data visualization since it enables visual interpretation of the dataset and the detection of patterns, correlations, and outliers. Histograms depict the frequency or count of observations within each bin to represent the distribution of a single numeric variable. They aid in determining the skewness, outlier presence, and distributional shape. Figure 6 shows a histogram of the distribution of each of the 10 features.

Figure 6: Feature Distribution of Dataset

A common visualization method in EDA is the use of heat maps, which employ color to depict data in a matrix or tabular format. A visual representation of the strength, size, or connection between two variables is given by heat maps. The pairwise correlation coefficients between variables are shown in a matrix format on a correlation heat map. Colors are used to depict the correlation's strength and direction. Warm colors are frequently used to depict positive correlations and cool colors are frequently used to represent negative correlations. The use of correlation heat maps allows for the detection of probable correlations by highlighting dependencies and relationships between variables. Figure 7 is an example of a heatmap, which is a visual representation of data that employs color coding to indicate the size of values in a matrix.

Figure 7: Heat Map Visualization of Data

3.4. Long Short-Term Memory Based Course Recommendation System

RNN is a type of ANN that operate on time series or sequential input. Similar to CNN and feedforward networks, it uses training data to learn. The web can influence current input and output while copying data from earlier inputs. The variables used in CNN are independent of one another. RNN determines the output based on the previous component.

An ordinary recurrent neural network is a feedforward neural network without time independency. The hidden nodes connecting to one another are given short-term memory. Some data will be retained from the previous time point for a brief period of time. The projected data may be deleted as the network continues to train, creating an extremely limited memory. The vanishing gradient issue is resolved via backpropagation learning across numerous hidden layers. An erroneous signal is constantly multiplied by the activation function. Backpropagation allows memory to retain data temporarily. Long-term memory is thus prevented. RNNs come in a variety of forms, including one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many.

An LSTM Neural Network, is mostly employed in deep learning, is one of the artificial neural networks of RNN [27]. LSTM has revolutionized machine learning and neurocomputing, notably enhancing Google's speech recognition, translation capabilities in Google Translate, and Amazon's Alexa responses. Facebook's utilization of LSTM for translations, surpassing 4 billion per day in 2017, underscores its widespread adoption and effectiveness. The model's success can be attributed to its adept handling of the challenging gradient problems inherent in training recurrent or deep neural networks, a factor pivotal to its superiority over previous recurrent architectures [28]. It can learn order dependencies in sequence prediction tasks. It is a particular kind of RNN that handles long-term interdependence and can tackle difficult issues. It identifies uses for which the input order is crucial. Many variants of Deep RNN have been created to address the problem of rapidly diminishing or excessively amplifying gradients. One of them, the LSTM [26], is a unique network. By establishing distinct activation functions for each Gate, long- and short-term memory try to recall the prior knowledge via which the network comes across and forgets irrelevant information. Additionally, it has a vector called internal cell state, which practically describes the knowledge that the prior unit has kept.

Figure 8: Basic Architecture of LSTM Unit

The mathematical model for LSTM networks involves a series of interconnected computational units, each with specific operations governing information flow. In essence, an LSTM unit comprises several components, including input gates, forget gates, output gates, and a cell state. These components are governed by mathematical equations that regulate the transmission of data across the network.

Here's a breakdown of the mathematical operations involved in an LSTM unit:

1. **Input Gate (i_t):** Decides which data from the present input ought to be retained within the cell state.
 - $i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$
 - Where i_t is the input gate activation, W_i represents weight matrices, h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state, x_t is the current input, and b_i is the bias vector.
2. **Forget Gate (f_t):** Determines which data from the cell state should be omitted or discarded.
 - $f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$
 - Where f_t is the forget gate activation, W_f represents weight matrices, h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state, x_t is the current input, and b_f is the bias vector.
3. **Candidate Cell State ($\sim C_t$):** Denotes potential new values that might be incorporated into the cell state.
 - $\sim C_t = \tanh(W_c \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c)$
 - Where $\sim C_t$ represents the candidate cell state, W_c represents weight matrices, h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state, x_t is the current input, and b_c is the bias vector.
4. **Update Cell State (C_t):** Integrates the data from both the forget and input gates to modify the cell state.
 - $C_t = f_t \cdot C_{t-1} + i_t \cdot \sim C_t$
 - Where C_t is the updated cell state, f_t represents the forget gate activation, C_{t-1} is the previous cell state, i_t represents the input gate activation, and $\sim C_t$ is the candidate cell state.
5. **Output Gate (o_t):** Determines which data from the cell state should be presented as output.
 - $o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$
 - Where o_t is the output gate activation, W_o represents weight matrices, h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state, x_t is the current input, and b_o is the bias vector.
6. **Hidden State (h_t):** Generates the result or output from the LSTM unit.
 - $h_t = o_t \cdot \tanh(C_t)$
 - Where h_t is the current hidden state, o_t represents the output gate activation, and C_t is the current cell state.

These equations govern the flow of information through an LSTM unit, allowing it to capture and utilize long-range dependencies in sequential data. Multiple LSTM units can be stacked together to form deeper architectures, enabling the network to learn increasingly complex patterns in sequential data.

There is only one LSTM layer in the proposed CRS. The layer has 128 LSTM units, which determines the size or the extent of the output realm. The LSTM layer is followed by a layer which is dense. On the

dense layer, which consists of 16 units, 'relu' activation function is implemented. The activation function provides the neural network with non-linear characteristics, allowing it to effectively grasp intricate patterns during the learning process. Table 3 contains the model summary of the proposed CRS.

Table 3: Model Summary

Total Parameters	68,624
Trainable Parameters	68,624
Non- Trainable Parameters	0

Figure 9 shows the proposed CRS that initialize with 11 features. After the suggested model has been processed, a final output with 16 classes (16 courses) is produced. For training, 30 epochs were used in this model. The optimal value at which the suggested model converges and the accuracy and loss remain stable, yielding the best results, is 30 epochs.

Figure 9: Architecture of Proposed Model

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Hardware and Software Setup

The recommended model was run subsequent to the preparation of the dataset. 2560 instances and 11 attributes are included in the dataset. Data splitting came after the data preprocessing. It is divided into two sets, training (80%) and testing (20%), with a total of 2048 instances in the training set and 512 instances in the testing set. LSTM was used to build, train, and assess the model using Google Collaboratory. Python and TensorFlow were utilized throughout the entire process. Within the suggested model, the optimization function employed was 'Adam'. The model was trained using a 64-batch size across 30 epochs.

4.2. Performance Parameters

Several performance parameters are frequently employed in deep learning to assess a model's efficiency. The selection of assessment criteria varies according to the particular task and the characteristics of the problem being addressed. Accuracy is a fundamental idea and a widely used evaluation metric across many subjects and fields. It is an important tool for evaluating the accuracy or precision of models, algorithms, systems, and predictions as well as their effectiveness and dependability. Accuracy offers a quantitative evaluation of how closely a given result conforms to the true or expected values, whether in the context of data analysis, machine learning, classification tasks, or scientific research. Accuracy is essentially the proportion of correctly classifying or predicting events to all instances or observations. It measures the degree of congruence between the estimated or anticipated values and the actual or reference values. More precise and reliable findings are implied by predictions that are more accurate because they are closer to the actual values. When evaluating the efficiency and performance of models, the loss value is crucial. The term "loss," also known as the "loss function" or "cost function," refers to the essential element that measures the difference between goal or ground truth values and predicted values. It gives an indication of a model's present performance and acts as a manual for refining and enhancing the model's accuracy. By calculating the difference between expected and actual values, loss functions are an essential tool in model optimization. During training, the model is fed input data, and predictions are compared to the measured values. The loss function determines the error, which is commonly expressed as a numerical value and reflects the discrepancy between the true and anticipated values. The proposed course recommendation model had an accuracy of 99.76% and a loss of 0.0133 after successful training. The accuracy and loss graphs provided in Figures 10 and 11 are used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed CRS.

Figure 10: Accuracy Plot of Proposed Model

The performance of a model or algorithm during training or testing is graphically represented by an accuracy plot. It shows that how accuracy varies as a result of parameter adjustments and learning,

which is often shown on the y-axis. The accuracy plot is frequently used in deep learning and machine learning projects to track the development and effectiveness of a model. It aids in determining how effectively the model learns from the input and generates precise predictions. The accuracy plot displays the evolution of the model's accuracy during training as iteratively updating its parameters depending on training data. The accuracy of the plot could be initially low before gradually increasing as the model learns and modifies. If the model is overfitting or underfitting the data, it can reveal insights into the convergence behavior of the model.

A loss plot is a graphical representation of the value of the loss function as it changes during model training or optimization. It offers a useful perspective on the model's performance and development over the course of training iterations or epochs. The training iterations or epochs are typically represented on the x-axis of a loss plot, which typically displays the value of the loss function on the y-axis. The loss plot displays how the loss value changes over time while the model is trained, providing a visual evaluation of the model's convergence and performance. A loss plot is particularly helpful for tracking the training process and spotting patterns or trends in the model's performance. The model makes unpredictable or poor predictions in the early phases of training, which could result in a relatively high loss value. Over the course of training, the loss value generally decreases, indicating that the model is assimilating fresh data and improving its predictive accuracy. The loss value should eventually converge to a minimum, and a loss map should ideally show a declining trend. This shows that the model is successfully tuning its parameters to reduce the difference between the predicted and true values. Table 4 lists some examples of course recommendations made using the suggested methodology.

Figure 11: Loss Plot of Proposed Model

Table 4: Sample Recommendation from Proposed Course Recommendation System

Input Data	Suggested Course
(8,0,1,1,1,62,72,62,82,82)	Computer Hardware Engineering
(1,0,0,0,0,61,71,81,91,81)	Chemical Engineering
(2,0,0,0,1,62,72,82,92,82)	Civil Engineering
(3,0,0,1,0,63,73,83,93,83)	Electrical Engineering
(4,0,0,1,1,64,74,84,94,84)	Mechanical Engineering

Taking a particular instance for the justification of the output; The following code is given

```
input = [2,0,0,0,1,62,72,82,92,82]
input_array = np.asarray(input)
input_resaped = input_array.reshape(1,-1)
prediction = model.predict(input_resaped)
pred = np.argmax(prediction, axis=1)
print(encoder.inverse_transform(pred))
```

- **Model Architecture:** The model architecture, is an LSTM-based neural network trained on a dataset of course sequences and their corresponding labels.
- **Input Features:** The input sequence [2,0,0,0,1,62,72,82,92,82] represents a sequence of features, the encoded representations of user interactions such as MBTI score, high school and high er secondary marks etc.
- **Model Prediction:** The predict method of the model is used to generate predictions based on the provided input sequence.
- **Decoder:** The predicted indices (e.g., class probabilities) are then decoded back into their original labels using an inverse transformation provided by an encoder. In this case, the label "Civil Engineering" corresponds to the highest predicted class probability.
- **Justification:** The model likely learned from the training data that sequences similar to the provided input sequence are associated with the label "Civil Engineering." This association might have been learned through patterns in the data, such as frequent sequences of course interactions or similarities in course attributes.

Overall, the model's prediction of "Civil Engineering" suggests that it has identified patterns in the input sequence indicative of courses related to Civil Engineering, based on its training on historical data.

5. Conclusion

Students can benefit greatly from an engineering CRS in order to navigate the huge selection of engineering course alternatives. The CRS is very important in the stream of education. Students receive individualized information from the recommendation system which helps them to choose the best engineering courses for their interests, academic objectives, and professional aspirations. With this

individualized approach, students may choose courses that suit their unique interests and longterm goals and they can achieve with confidence. In this paper, an effective engineering CRS employing LSTM was proposed and on a student dataset, the suggested model is evaluated. The model is trained using the data from 16 distinct engineering courses. Based on ten features, the suggested system is utilized to predict engineering courses. To enhance prediction performance, a dense layer was added to the suggested LSTM model. The results of the experiment showed that the suggested engineering CRS beat conventional recommendation systems and achieved an accuracy of 99.76%. Future study may include hybrid architectures for CRS.

References

7. Subasman, Iman & Rusmiati Aliyyah, Rusi. (2023). The Impact of Technological Transformation On Career Choices In The Stem Sector. *Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan dan Psikologi*. 1. 129-142. 10.61397/jkpp.v1i2.94.
8. Olivia P. Almario, (2021) Factors Affecting the Career Choice Decision of Shs In Central Luzo, *Cosmos An International Journal of Management, A Refereed Research Journal*, Vol 11 / No 1 / Jul-Dec, ISSN: 2278-1218.
9. EREMIE, Maxwell D. & IBIFARI, Blessing (2018). "Factors Influencing Students' Career Choice in Secondary Schools In Rivers State: Implication For Career Counselling", *International Journal of Innovative Education Research* 6(4):93-100, Oct.-Dec., ISSN: 2354-2942.
10. Abe, E.N., Chikoko V (2020). Exploring the factors that influence the career decision of STEM students at a university in South Africa. *IJ STEM Ed* 7, 60. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00256-x>. 2
11. Zakira Jahantab (2021) "Role Of Education In National Development", *Pakistan Journal of Applied Social Sciences*, Vol. 12(1), pp.87-108, ISSN: 2409-0077(Print), ISSN: 2663-8894(Online).
12. Sagar, Sarparaj. (2023). role of education on the economic development of india. 10.13140/RG.2.2.29634.76487.
13. Furnham, A. (2020). Myers-Briggs type indicator (MBTI). *Encyclopedia of personality and individual differences*, 3059-3062.
14. John, Romel & John, Rehana & Rao, Zia-ur-Rehman. (2020). The big five personality traits and academic performance. *Journal of Law & Social Studies*. 2. 10-19. 10.52279/jlss.02.01.1019.
15. Huynh-Ly, Thanh-Nhan & Nguyen, Huu-Hoa & Thai-Nghe, Nguyen. (2016). Methods for building course recommendation systems. 163-168. 10.1109/KSE.2016.7758047.
16. Zhang, Hao & Yang, Heng & Huang, Tao & Zhan, Gaoqiang. (2017). DBNCF: Personalized Courses Recommendation System Based on DBN in MOOC Environment. 106-108. 10.1109/ISET.2017.33.
17. Ma, B., Lu, M., Taniguchi, Y., & Konomi, S. I. (2021). CourseQ: the impact of visual and interactive course recommendation in university environments. *Research and practice in technology enhanced learning*, 16, 1-24.

18. Li, Q., & Kim, J. (2021). A deep learning-based course recommender system for sustainable development in education. *Applied Sciences*, 11(19), 8993.
19. Dahdouh, Karim & Oughdir, Lahcen & Dakkak, Ahmed & Abdelali, Ibriz. (2018). Smart Courses Recommender System for Online Learning Platform. 328-333. 10.1109/CIST.2018.8596516.
20. Lalitha, T. B., & Sreeja, P. S. (2020). Personalized self-directed learning recommendation system. *Procedia Computer Science*, 171, 583-592.
21. Wang, Ren & Zaïane, Osmar. (2018). Sequence-Based Approaches to Course Recommender Systems: 29th International Conference, DEXA 2018, Regensburg, Germany, September 3–6, 2018, Proceedings, Part I. 10.1007/978-3-319-98809-2_3.
22. Qamhieh, M., Sammaneh, H., & Demaidi, M. N. (2020). PCRS: personalized career-path recommender system for engineering students. *IEEE Access*, 8, 214039-214049.
23. Masika, Robert & Rono, Dr & Kati, Dr. (2022). Classification Algorithm for Career Recommendation System. *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*. 11. 91-97. 10.7753/IJCATR1104.1002.
24. Li Q, Kim J. (2021). A Deep Learning-Based Course Recommender System for Sustainable Development in Education. *Applied Sciences*. 2021; 11(19):8993. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11198993>.
25. Feng, Jianwen & Lin, Xuan. (2022). Research on Online Learners' Course Recommendation System Based on Knowledge Atlas in Smart Education Cloud Platform. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*. 1-8. 10.1155/2022/5043838.
26. Amane, M., Aissaoui, K., & Berrada, M. (2021). A multi-agent and content-based course recommender system for university e-learning platforms. In *Digital Technologies and Applications: Proceedings of ICDTA 21, Fez, Morocco* (pp. 663-672). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
27. Ibrahim, M. E., Yang, Y., & Ndzi, D. (2017). Using ontology for personalised course recommendation applications. In *Computational Science and Its Applications—ICCSA 2017: 17th International Conference, Trieste, Italy, July 3-6, 2017, Proceedings, Part I 17* (pp. 426-438).
28. Al-Asadi, Ammar & Elameer, Amer. (2018). Design and Evaluation of a Course Recommender System Using Content-Based Approach. 1-6. 10.1109/ICOASE.2018.8548789.
29. Tan, J., Chang, L., Liu, T., & Zhao, X. (2020). Attentional autoencoder for course recommendation in mooc with course relevance. In *2020 International Conference on Cyber-Enabled Distributed Computing and Knowledge Discovery (CyberC)* (pp. 190-196). IEEE.
30. Vijay S V, Pradeep S2, Sathish N3, "Personality Prediction System", *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 4, no 10, pp 1707-1717 October (2023), ISSN 2582-7421.
31. N A Deraman, "Covid19 and Higher Education: A Degree Course Recommender System Based on Personality Using Rule-Based", *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 704 (2021) 012021, doi:10.1088/1755-1315/704/1/012021.

32. B. Nath Saha and A. Senapati, "Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) based Deep Learning for Sentiment Analysis of English and Spanish Data," 2020 International Conference on Computational Performance Evaluation (ComPE), Shillong, India, 2020, pp. 442-446, doi: 10.1109/ComPE49325.2020.9200054.
33. Oruh, Jane & Viriri, Serestina & Adegun, Adekanmi. (2022). Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Network for Automatic Speech Recognition. IEEE Access. 10. 30069-30079. 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3159339.
34. Van Houdt, Greg & Mosquera, Carlos & Nápoles, Gonzalo. (2020). A Review on the Long Short-Term Memory Model. Artificial Intelligence Review. 53. 10.1007/s10462-020-09838-1.